

The experiment was in duplicate plots (ABBA method) with seven replications. GR-11 seedlings were transplanted in 50-m² plots. Egg masses were counted in need-based plots at 10-d intervals. When 1 fresh egg mass was observed in any plot, all replications were sprayed with monocrotophos 0.36 kg ai/ ha. In schedule-based control plots, the same insecticide formulation was applied 15, 45, and 60 d after transplanting.

Percentage of deadhearts at maximum tillering, number of whiteheads at reproductive stage, and grain yield were recorded, and the data were statistically and economically analyzed.

In 1983, mean percentage of deadhearts was 2.9 in the need-based treatment and 6.4 in the schedule-based treatment (Table 1). The trend was similar in 1984. The number of whiteheads also was significantly lower in need-based than in schedule-based treatments. The need-based treatment had 10 and 15% higher yield in 1983 and

Table 1. Efficiency of need-based control of YSB compared with schedule-based insecticide application, Gujarat, India, 1983 and 1984.^a

Insecticide application	Mean percentage deadhearts		Mean no. whiteheads		Mean grain yield (t/ha)	
	1983	1984	1983	1984	1983	1984
Need-based	2.9 a	3.6 a	75 a	93 a	3.7 a	5.6 a
Schedule-based	6.4 b	6.0 b	102 b	168 b	3.3 b	4.7 b
't' value	2.54	4.09	2.44	3.16	2.71	8.84

^aSeparation of means in a column at the 5% level.

Table 2. Economics of need-based control of YSB, Gujarat, India.

Insecticide application	Total cost of insecticides and labor ^b (\$/ha)		Gross income (\$/ha)		Net gain over check (\$/ha)		Incremental cost benefit ratio (additional profit per \$ cost)	
	1983	1984	1983	1984	1983	1984	1983	1984
Need-based ^a	38	50	565	863	54	132	0.42	1.64
Schedule-based	36	36	511	730	—	—	—	—

^aThree sprays were necessary in 1983 and four in 1984. ^bLabor cost for sampling and applying insecticides.

1984, and higher net return and cost benefit ratio (Table 2).

The appropriate YSB egg mass

threshold level per unit area should be determined. \mathcal{L}

Virulence of whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) populations in South and Southeast Asia: report of a collaborative project

E.A. Heinrichs, H.R. Rapusas, and G.S. Khush, IRRI; S. Chelliah and K. Gunathilagaraj, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore, India; S. Uthamorang, Aduthurai, Tamil Nadu, India; W.S. Akib, MORIF, Maros, Sulawesi, Indonesia; S. Y. Choi, College of Agriculture, Seoul National University, Suweon, Korea; S. Pongprasert, Rice Research Institute, Bangkok, Thailand; W. Katanyukul, Entomology and Zoology Division, Bangkok, Thailand; and N. K. Huynh and T.H. Tien, University of Cantho, Vietnam

WBPH *Sogatella furcifera* Horváth outbreaks appear to have increased in frequency and severity throughout Asia. Resistant varieties, which should play a key role in WBPH control, have not been developed. More than 400 traditional varieties with WBPH resistance have been identified in greenhouse screening at IRRI and in national programs in South and

Table 1. Summary of damage ratings of varieties with genes for resistance in seedbox screening for WBPH.

Variety	Gene	Reaction ^a at					
		Philippines IRRI	India Tamil Nadu	Indonesia Maros	Korea Suweon	Thailand Bangkok	Vietnam Cantho
N22	<i>Wbph 1</i>	R	R	R	R	R	MR
ARC10239	<i>Wbph 2</i>	R	R	R	R	R	S
IR2035-117-3	<i>Wbph 1 + Wbph 2</i>	R	R	R	MR	R	MR
WC1240	<i>Wbph 1 + 1 recessive</i>	R	R	R	R	R	MR
Colombo	<i>Wbph 2 + 1 recessive</i>	R	R	R	R	R	MR
TN1	None	S	S	S	S	S	S

^aR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, S = susceptible.

Table 2. Feeding activity of WBPH female adults as indicated by honeydew excretion (area of honeydew spot in mm²)^a on varieties with different genes for resistance.

Variety	Honeydew spot (mm ²)					
	Philippines IRRI	India Coimbatore	Indonesia Maros	Korea Suweon	Thailand Bangkok	Vietnam Cantho
N22	28 a	77 b	3 a	6 a	9 a	47 ab
ARC10239	21 a	95 b	5 a	7 a	45 a	69 b
IR2035-117-3	10 a	8 a	4 a	0 a	46 a	—
WC1240	44 a	14 a	26 a	2 a	41 a	23 a
Colombo	27 a	37 ab	5 a	0 a	151 b	42 ab
TN1	714 b	367 c	116 b	49 b	269 c	121 c

^aAv of 5 replications. Separation of means in a column by Duncan's multiple range test at the 5% level.

Southeast Asia. Genetics studies at IRRI have identified several genes for resistance to the Philippine population.

There have been reports of differential reactions of resistant varieties to WBPH populations in South and Southeast Asia. In breeding for WBPH resistance, it is important to select parents that have resistance to local populations. Materials for use in several countries should have resistance to a diversity of WBPH populations.

We determined the response of varieties with different genes for WBPH resistance to help breeders select parent varieties with broad WBPH resistance. IRRI-developed high yielding lines with WBPH resistance also were evaluated in several countries.

The gene sources given in Table 1 were evaluated in six countries using seedbox screening, feeding, and population growth tests. IR2035-117-3 is a resistant check. Its progeny — IR15527-21-2-3, IR15529-253-2-2-2, and IR15795-151-2-3-2-2— showed WBPH resistance in tests throughout South and Southeast Asia.

All gene sources in seedbox evaluation were resistant or moderately resistant at the various locations, except ARC10239 which was susceptible in Vietnam (Table 1). The other varieties were moderately resistant in Vietnam and most were resistant at the other locations.

All resistant varieties significantly reduced WBPH feeding (Table 2). At IRRI and in Indonesia, there was no difference among the resistant cultivars.

The survival test showed fewer WBPH on resistant varieties than on susceptible TN1, except on N22 at IRRI and in Vietnam (Table 3). Although ARC10239 was susceptible in seedbox screening in Vietnam, very few WBPH survived on it.

In population growth tests, all cultivars except N22 at IRRI significantly reduced WBPH populations below those on TN1 (Table 4). Among test cultivars, populations on N22 were generally among the highest. At IRRI, IR2035-117-3 had the lowest population and performed similarly in India, Korea, and Thailand.

Table 3. WBPH survival^a on varieties with different genes for resistance.

Variety	Survival (%)					
	Philippines IRRI	India Coimbatore	Korea Suweon	Thailand		Vietnam Cantho
				Entomology and Zoology Division Bangkok	Thai Rice Research Institute Bangkok	
N22	96 b	40 b	43 b	10 a	66 b	48 bc
ARC10239	68 a	34 b	24 ab	18 a	66 b	14 a
IR2035-117-3	70 a	16 a	20 a	12 a	58 b	—
WC1240	86 ab	40 b	19 a	10 a	42 a	17 a
Colombo	82 ab	44 b	19 a	6 a	58 b	28 ab
TN1	96 b	72 c	60 c	68 b	96 c	70 c

^aAv of 5 replications. Determined at 15 d after inoculation. Separation of means in a column by Duncan's multiple range test at the 5% level.

Table 4. Population growth^a of WBPH on varieties with different genes for resistance.

Variety	Population growth (no./pair)				
	Philippines IRRI	India Coimbatore	Korea Suweon	Thailand	
				Entomology and Zoology Division Bangkok	Rice Research Institute Bangkok
N22	307 cd	61 b	11 a	8 a	219 c
ARC10239	192 bc	24 a	0 a	11 a	226 c
IR2035-117-3	33 a	17 a	0 a	4 a	163 b
WC1240	126 b	23 a	0 a	4 a	125 a
Colombo	86 b	28 a	0 a	9 a	233 c
TN1	559 d	104 c	202 b	44 b	782 d

^aAv of 5 replications, determined at 30 d after inoculation. Separation of means in a column by Duncan's multiple range test at the 5% level.

Data show that all the varieties with genes for resistance to the Philippine WBPH population also are resistant or moderately resistant in India, Indonesia, Korea, Thailand, and Vietnam. IR2035-117-3, with *Wbph 1* and *Wbph 2*, has been extensively used as parent at IRRI.

Many breeding lines developed from IR2035-117-3 were resistant at all of the locations tested. If differential responses of resistant varieties to WBPH populations throughout Asia are a constraint to breeding, it was not apparent in this study. *ℵ*

A carbon dioxide-cone (CO₂NE) sampler for arthropods in flooded rice

G. B. Aquino and E. A. Heinrichs,
Entomology Department, IRRI

We developed a CO₂NE arthropod sampler for obtaining absolute estimates in research plots.

The sampler consists of a portable CO₂ tank with a rubber hose to deliver gas, an aluminum cone, a strainer with an attached plastic vial with a nylon mesh bottom, and an enclosure ring.

The aluminum cone is carefully placed over a rice hill followed by the enclosure ring. The cone is then filled with CO₂ (see photos). A rubber stopper seals off the opening at the top of the cone. After 1-2 min the cone is removed. The arthropods that fell onto the water within the enclosure ring are scooped up with the strainer and collected in the attached vial. Arthropods that fall between tillers are flushed out with water. When sampling is complete, the arthropods in the vial are rinsed out through another vial with 75% alcohol and brought to the laboratory.